

UROLITHIASIS UROLITHIAS CLASSIFICATION – TYPES AND COMPOSITION OF STONES IN UROLITHIAS DISEASE

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Relevance: urolithiasis are common type of urological disease, accounting for approximately 12% of the population. The increasing incidence of the disease is associated with risks such as chronic kidney disease and end-stage renal failure. The literature provides a classification of stones based on the chemical composition, types of stones, etiology, and risk factors. According to the World Health Organization, stones are classified according to their composition as follows: calcium-based stones (75–85% oxalate or phosphate), uric acid stones (5–10%), struvite stones (5–15%, associated with infection) and cysteine stones (1–2%). Urolithiasis is the formation of stones of various sizes in the urinary tract due to the deposition of chemical substances due to metabolic disorders. The recurrence rate of urolithiasis is up to 50% every 5 years.

Objective of the study: to study the classification of urolithiasis, stone types and chemical composition.

Materials and methods: the study used methods related to urolithiasis in the world and the Republic of Uzbekistan, statistical data, literature, retrospective clinical, and comparative analysis methods.

Results: the classification of urolithiasis, i.e. urinary stone disease, is usually based on the chemical composition of the stones, which determines the etiology, risk factors and treatment strategies. Based on the Global Burden of Disease studies conducted by the World Health Organization and its partners, the global prevalence of the disease was studied in 204 countries, and the age-standardized incidence rate decreased by 17.5% (14.7–20.0) in 1990–2019, but an increase is observed in hot regions due to climate change and environmental factors. In Uzbekistan, Central Asian countries, environmental factors (dry climate, water salinity, a sharp decrease in the Aral Sea) can increase the prevalence of the disease from 4–5% to 7–8%, which leads to dehydration and increased mineralization.

Summary literature according to the analysis, it was found that the classification of urolithiasis, the types and composition of stones in urolithiasis are different in different states, countries, and regions. Based on this analysis, we will study the distribution and epidemiology of urolithiasis in different regions.

Table

Used literature

Type	Prevalence	Common Causes/Risk Factors	Formation Mechanism	Management Notes
Calcium (oxalate/phosphate)	70–80 percent	Hypercalciuria, hyperoxaluria, obesity, metabolic syndrome	Supersaturation on Randall's plaques	Hydration, diet; lithotripsy/URS for larger stones
Uric acid	8–10 percent	High-purine diet, gout, acidic urine	Free-particles in tubules	Alkalinization, allopurinol

Struvite	7–15 percent	Bacterial infections (urease producers)	Alkaline urine precipitation	Antibiotics, surgical removal
In the end	1–2 percent	Genetic (Cystinuria)	Amino acid reabsorption defect	Fluid intake, chelators like tiopronin

Causes and Risk Factors

Formation involves urine supersaturation, nucleation, growth, aggregation, and retention, influenced by crystallization promoters/inhibitors and cellular injury. General risks: dehydration, high-sodium/protein diets, genetics, hot climates. Type-specific: monogenetic for cysteine, others (4 percent of adults). Oxidative stress and osteogenesis factors may contribute.

Conclusions: urolithiasis is a multifaceted pathology that occurs as a result of complex etiological factors. Its classification and identification of causes are important in clinical practice and serve as the basis for developing individualized treatment and effective preventive measures. Studies conducted in recent years show that the metabolic and genetic aspects of urolithiasis require a deeper study. Also, the formation of a healthy lifestyle and dietary habits is important in preventing the disease.